

X-ray absorption and magnetic circular dichroism characterization of a novel ferromagnetic MnN_x phase in $\text{Mn}/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multilayers

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ABSTRACT

Ferromagnetism above room temperature has been observed in $\text{Mn}/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multilayered films for the first time. Characterization of the structural and electronic properties was performed to study the ferromagnetic behavior of this system. X-ray absorption spectroscopy at the Mn K and L edges, as well as x-ray magnetic circular dichroism, evidences the presence of divalent Mn in the films. X-ray absorption near edge structure measurements, which are compared to calculations, confirms the presence of a slightly distorted Mn_3N_2 phase that is proposed to be the origin of the ferromagnetism in this system.

Mn-doped semiconductors such as $\text{Mn}:\text{InAs}$, $\text{Mn}:\text{GaAs}$, and especially $\text{Mn}:\text{GaN}$ have attracted considerable attention with the perspective of designing diluted magnetic semiconductors (DMSs) with high Curie temperatures. In this area, MnN_x phases have gained great interest due to existing doubts concerning the homogeneity of ternary $\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{N}$ alloys and possible formation of different MnN_x phases as the possible origin of the observed ferromagnetism.¹ Special attention has been directed to the manganese mononitride θ - MnN phase since phase-separated inclusions or MnN-rich regions in the matrix can have the same crystallographic structure as the host. Although MnN is known to have a tetragonally distorted NaCl structure with an antiferromagnetic (AF) ground state,² it has been shown theoretically that a ferromagnetic (FM) arrangement of the spins can be established depending on the polymorph of MnN and the lattice constant. Several theoretical studies on MnN in the hypothetical zinc-blende and wurtzite structures have aimed to obtain a better understanding of the GaMnN and InMnN DMSs.^{1,3}

Recently, simulations of GaN/MnN superlattices have been developed as a new way to obtain the FM wurtzite w - MnN on GaN as an alternative to the (Ga, Mn)N DMS approach.⁴ These calculations have suggested that this system could be suitable for new spintronics devices by providing spin-polarized carriers in the wide-gap nitride system. A FM ground state has been predicted in these GaN/MnN heterostructures, which comprise a thin layer of biaxially strained w - MnN intercalated with layers of GaN, due to the structural relaxation in the GaN–MnN interface. Nonetheless, until now there have been no experimental attempts to produce the FM semiconductor/manganese nitride heterostructures. Here, because of its similarities, instead of GaN, we employ Si_3N_4 , which also possesses a wide-band-gap semiconducting behavior and can be an excellent host material permitting high dopant concentrations.^{5,6}

We have carried out an experimental investigation concerning the magnetic properties of nominal $\text{Mn}/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multilayers prepared by sputtering. In this letter, we report the characterization with x-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) and x-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) of these $\text{Mn}/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multilayered films that exhibit FM ordering above room temperature (RT). XAS identifies the Mn valence state and local environment, and XMCD provides an element-specific tool sensitive to the magnetic states. Additional *ab initio* calculations of the x-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) have been performed to confirm the presence of a MnN_x phase at the mentioned Mn layer, which is proposed as the origin of FM behavior.

The $\text{Mn}/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multilayers were prepared by sequential sputtering of Si_3N_4 and Mn on Si(100) substrates at RT. Several samples with general formula $[\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4(3 \text{ nm})/\text{Mn}(t)]_n$ were grown, starting with a Si_3N_4 layer and terminating with an additional 3 nm Si_3N_4 layer deposited on top. The number of bilayers (n) was progressively increased (from 5 to 75) as the Mn layer thickness (t) was reduced (from nominally 6 to 0.2 nm) in order to maintain the total amount of Mn approximately constant. The residual pressure in the vacuum system was 1×10^{-7} mbar. The Si_3N_4 layers were deposited by reactive rf sputtering from a pure Si target (99.999%) with N_2 as reactive sputtering gas.⁷ The deposition rate was 2 nm/min for a rf power of 100 W. The Mn was deposited by dc sputtering from a Mn target (99.95%) with Ar as sputtering working gas and a deposition rate of ~ 4 nm/min for a dc power of ~ 10 W.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), as shown in Fig. 1(a), confirms that the sample has a multilayered structure. However, the Mn can be incorporated into the semiconductor layer in samples where the layer thickness, diffusion length, and interface roughness are of comparable size. X-ray reflectivity shows hardly any nanoscaled periodicity for samples with small t , evidencing an intermixing of the Si_3N_4 and Mn layers at the low range of Mn thickness.

FIG. 1. TEM cross sections of (a) $[\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4(3 \text{ nm}) / \text{Mn}(3 \text{ nm})]_{10}$ and (b) $[\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4(3 \text{ nm}) / \text{Mn}(0.7 \text{ nm})]_{43}$ samples.

Due to the tendency of Si_3N_4 to develop the corresponding oxynitride, determination of the oxygen content in the films is of great importance since it can strongly affect the physical properties.⁷ Nuclear reaction analysis measurements give 3 at. % oxygen in the $t = 0.4 \text{ nm}$ sample and, within the resolution limit, no oxygen in the $t = 0.2 \text{ nm}$ sample. The reason for this low oxygen content—an advantage in the study of the Mn/ Si_3N_4 system—lies in the deposition method (reactive sputtering of Si), as opposed to deposition from Si_3N_4 ceramic targets.⁸

Magnetic characterization was performed from 5 to 400 K using a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometer (Quantum Design MPMS-5S). Figure 2 shows magnetic hysteresis loops measured at 5 and 300 K, where the diamagnetic contribution of the Si substrate has been subtracted. The magnetization per manganese atom was calculated accounting for the precise amount of Mn as obtained by Rutherford backscattering spectroscopy (RBS). The results show that the films exhibit FM order at RT. The $t = 0.2 \text{ nm}$ sample shows a higher saturation magnetization value of $\sim 0.1 \mu_B/\text{Mn}$. The $M(T)$ curve of the $t = 0.4 \text{ nm}$ sample (inset in Fig. 2) evidences a Curie temperature above 400 K. The coercive field of these samples varies from about 80 to 130 Oe at 5 K and from 60 to 75 Oe at RT.

The Mn local electronic structure was investigated by XAS at the Mn K edge, carried out on beamline BM8 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble. Spectra were collected at RT in total electron yield (TEY) mode. Figure 3 shows the normalized XANES spectrum of the $t = 0.2 \text{ nm}$ sample. The threshold energy position evidences an average Mn oxidation state close to $2+$. The extended x-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) at the Mn K edge was analyzed using the VIPER software⁹ in order to obtain precise information about the local environment of the Mn. The Fourier transform (FT) of the EXAFS was obtained using amplitude and phase backscattering functions calculated with the FEFF6 code.¹⁰ The results of the EXAFS analysis are shown in the inset of Fig. 3. The Mn–N pair distance (R) is 2.06 Å and the neighbors coordination (N) is slightly higher than 3.

FIG. 2. Hysteresis loops of $[\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4(3 \text{ nm}) / \text{Mn}(t)]_{75}$ samples. The insets show the low field region loop and the magnetization curve.

Mn $L_{3,2}$ edge XAS and XMCD measurements were done on beamline 5U.1 of the Synchrotron Radiation Source at Daresbury Laboratory. Spectra were collected in TEY mode reversing the applied magnetic field of $\pm 0.6 \text{ T}$ perpendicular to the surface at each data point for fixed photon helicity. Figure 4 shows the XAS and XMCD spectra of the $t = 0.2 \text{ nm}$ sample measured at RT. The Mn $L_{3,2}$ XAS structure is a fingerprint for the $3d$ count, giving information on the Mn valence state. The comparison with theoretical calculations for different electronic configurations¹¹ indicates that the $3d^n \rightarrow 2p^5 3d^{n+1}$ absorption spectrum corresponds to a $\text{Mn}^{2+} d^5$ ground state. The results sustain a noncentrosymmetrical T_d Mn environment with a crystal field close to $10Dq \approx 0.5 \text{ eV}$, in agreement with the EXAFS results. The difference between the XAS spectra recorded for parallel and antiparallel alignments of magnetic field and photon helicity results in a small XMCD signal for the $t = 0.2 \text{ nm}$ sample. Reversal of the XMCD signal was confirmed by switching between left and right circular polarizations. A

seven-point smooth of the dichroic signal is shown in Fig. 4, in comparison with the d^5 calculation. The XMCD signal shows that the magnetism arises from a Mn d^5 contribution, which has its largest value at the photon energy position of the XAS peak maximum.

FIG. 3. Mn K -edge XANES spectrum of $[\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4(3 \text{ nm}) / \text{Mn}(0.2 \text{ nm})]_{75}$ (black closed circles) compared with the spectrum of $[\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4(3 \text{ nm}) / \text{Mn}(6 \text{ nm})]_5$ (red open circles), where the metallic Mn contribution is notable (cf. α -Mn curve). The inset shows the EXAFS FT of the $t=0.2 \text{ nm}$ sample and its simulation.

FIG. 4. Mn $L_{3,2}$ XAS and XMCD spectra of $[\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4(3 \text{ nm}) / \text{Mn}(0.2 \text{ nm})]_{75}$ measured at RT and compared to calculations for Mn d^5 in T_d symmetry.

The combined results allow us to deduce how the Mn^{2+} cations bonded to nitrogen lead to FM order and what the role of the silicon-nitride matrix is. First, ferromagnetism caused by Mn metallic clusters can be ruled out. Furthermore, formation of ternary phases such as MnSiN_2 (Ref. 12) seems quite doubtful due to the silicon film content extracted from the RBS measurements. On the other hand, substitution of Si^{4+} by Mn^{2+} in Si_3N_4 seems rather unlikely due to the difference in ionic radii and considerable charge mismatch. Si sites are fourfold coordinated in Si_3N_4 with Si-N distances of $\sim 1.74 \text{ \AA}$. The Mn^{2+} ionic radius (0.80 \AA) in T_d symmetry greatly differs from the Si^{4+} radius (0.40 \AA). Large lattice distortions which could accomplish a reduction in the coordination number and relieve the possible charge mismatch might be considered. Even though, the large Mn-N distance (2.06 \AA) obtained by EXAFS hardly matches with the Mn^{2+} replacement in Si_3N_4 . Therefore, FM due to Mn^{2+} substitution into the Si_3N_4 matrix can be ruled out.

The formation of manganese nitrides such as $s\text{-Mn}_4\text{N}$, $\beta\text{-Mn}_2\text{N}$, or $\beta\text{-Mn}_5\text{N}_2$ phases can be rejected due to the large dissimilarity in the Mn-N atomic distance. Nonetheless, ferromagnetism due to the formation of a distorted $\theta\text{-MnN}$ phase should be considered here.

$\theta\text{-MnN}$ has a tetragonally distorted rocksalt structure, where Mn has octahedral (O_h) symmetry and a Mn-N distance of 2.098 \AA (Ref. 13) with an AF ground state.² However, depending on the polymorph and lattice constant, theoretical calculations predicted FM order, e.g., in the zinc-blende structure, which would exhibit shorter Mn-N distances and Mn T_d symmetry.⁴ The $\theta\text{-MnN}$ compound has a tendency to lose nitrogen, forming the $\beta\text{-Mn}_3\text{N}_2$ phase,¹³ which presents similar Mn-N distances.¹⁴

In the case of Mn/ Si_3N_4 films, the Mn-N distance of Å obtained by EXAFS is slightly shorter than the average in $\beta\text{-Mn}_3\text{N}_2$ (2.1 \AA). Taking into account previous theoretical calculations,^{1,3,4} which allow FM order in manganese nitrides with Mn

in T_d symmetry, the obtained results suggest that the origin of the FM behavior in Mn/Si₃N₄ multilayers is the formation of a distorted -Mn₃N₂ phase at the interfaces which seems to be favored by the Si₃N₄ tetrahedral structure.

Finally, additional *ab initio* calculations of the Mn *K*-edge XANES were performed for Mn metal, θ -MnN (Mn O_h environment), and η -Mn₃N₂ (Mn in two different environments: fivefold pyramids and linear twofold coordination with a ratio of 2:1). The results are compared to the experimental spectrum of the $t=6$ nm and the $t=0.2$ nm samples in Fig. 3. Feature D, a characteristic of metallic Mn, is observed for sample $t = 6$ nm, whose spectral profile evidences both metallic and nitride contributions, while no sign of Mn metallic phase appears in the $t = 0.2$ nm spectrum, exhibiting just nitride contribution. By comparing the $t = 0.2$ nm data with the computed nitride spectra, both θ -MnN and η -Mn₃N₂ show similar oscillations in the high energy region. However, their spectral profile at the threshold region differs, especially for the pre-edge A peak. This peak is experimentally observed and typically assigned to a non-centrosymmetric environment of the absorbing site such as in T_d symmetry. The theoretical simulation reproduces this peak for Mn₃N₂ while it is absent for MnN. These results indicate the presence of η -Mn₃N₂ in our samples. The fact that for increasing Mn thickness the relative contribution of η Mn₃N₂ in the XANES is reduced compared to that of bulklike Mn indicates that the Mn nitride formation in the sputtered Mn layer is related to the Si₃N₄ interfaces, leading, for thin enough Mn layers, to all the deposited Mn turned into manganese nitride. For the sake of understanding, this has been schematically represented in the insets of Fig. 1.

In conclusion, FM behavior above RT is reported for the first time in Mn/Si₃N₄ multilayers. The magnetic, structural, and electronic properties of this system have been investigated using SQUID, XAS, and XMCD. Mn $L_{3,2}$ XAS shows that divalent Mn, compatible with a noncentrosymmetric environment, is present in the films. XMCD shows that the magnetism is due to a Mn d^5 state. XANES calculations confirm the presence of a -Mn₃N₂ phase, where Mn is coordinated by fivefold nitrogen pyramids. Lastly, taking into account all the experimental results, the origin of ferromagnetism in these multilayers seems to originate from the formation of a distorted noncentrosymmetric η -Mn₃N₂ phase with slightly shorter Mn-N distances. Changes in the unit cell volume are commonly considered theoretically in order to obtain transitions to a FM phase from the AFM ground state in manganese nitrides.^{3,15}

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